

Citrus Peel: A valuable waste needing gentle treatment

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Abstract

Citrus is the most important fruit crop in the world with a production estimated at 89 million tons in 2014. Approximately 26% of citrus fruits are industrially processed into juice. Peel is generated as a major by-product of processing citrus fruits.

Citrus peel is composed of external part (flavedo), which is particularly rich in essential oils and carotenoids, and the internal spongy part (albedo), which is rich in pectin and phenols. A number of added value products which may prevent or contribute to the cure of many chronic diseases can be extracted from citrus peel. Such extracts can also be used as natural additives, as sweeteners, as colorants, etc. Citrus essential oils are often extracted by cold-pressing and/or vacuum-distillation. According to the literature, vacuum-distillation, which uses low extraction temperature to extract the oil, is considered to be the best for producing natural fragrance and essential oils with high production efficiency and improved quality of the product. Vacuum fractional distillation proved to be an effective method to perform a partial deterpenation of the citrus *sinensis* raw essential oil. No evidence of thermal and sunlight degradation in the raw oil was found.

In this work, methods of valorization of citrus peel waste from juice industries are proposed. The medicinal properties of citrus essential oils are presented and their quality as a function of the method of extraction is discussed.

Keywords: orange, lemon, essential oils, extraction, vacuum distillation

1. INTRODUCTION

Citrus belongs to the largest genus in the family Rutaceae and is the most traded horticultural product worldwide. Citrus fruits production is around 80 million tonnes per year. 34% of that is transformed into juices and especially in the major producing countries (Brazil and US), this percentage can be 96%. The juice yield of citrus fruits is about half of the fruit weight and that leads to the production of enormous byproducts every year, where the peel is taking the lead and is generally thrown away.

The peel that represents almost the other half of the fruit mass contains the highest concentration of flavonoids in citrus fruit. Also, it constitutes a good source of pectin, molasses, limonene and cold-pressed oils and mixed with dried pulps, it can be used as cattle feed. It is characterized by its antioxidant activity. Limonene is a phytochemical with anti-cancer effects and help with the heart burn. Citrus peels are full of immune-boosting vitamin C, bone-building calcium and anti-inflammatory bioflavonoids. They also include potassium that keeps blood pressure in healthy level.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Citrus peels were obtained from Arta, Greece. The procedure began with separation of the peel in two parts, the inside white part (albedo) and the outside orange part (flavedo). Flavedo mass was collected in the form of pulp. It was again split in two parts. The first one was dried naturally in low temperature, under atmosphere conditions and was subjected to valuable products extraction with pure alcohol. Maceration and percolation were following in order to isolate the desirable constituents. Quality controls were made during the procedure to validate the quality of the each stage of production. The final step consisted of evaporation of the solvent which had been used and the determination of the active compounds. The condensed product is ready was ready for use.

The second part of fresh mass was placed directly on the distiller. Steam distillation was chosen. Essential oils were thus separated.

3. OUR PRODUCTS

From the extracts and the essential oils a variety of products are produced. The essential oil is used in aromatherapy for relaxation and revitalization. The extract is a key ingredient in expectorants and mucolytic syrups. It is also a source of vitamin C in multivitamin formulations such as capsules. Last but not least orange oil is used in cosmetic products such as lotions and face tonic serum.

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